

CONTEXT AND THEMATIC ISSUES IN *THE STRANGER* BY ALBERT CAMUS

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Abstract

Works of literature rarely exist in a socio-historical vacuum. Interpreting them often always relies on our knowledge of the context of their production and the issues in the context they present through textual manipulation. It, therefore, presupposes knowing the artist's life and historical circumstances surrounding the work. The publication of *The Stranger* by Albert Camus in 1942 has continued to garner widespread interest and criticism due to its significant contextual issues. Eight decades to date, contextual issues of this classic work have remained relevant before, during, and after its production. Textual techniques such as the use of language and symbols have contextual implications. Rather than a dichotomy, text, and context play a complementary role in the overall aesthetic of the work. Context-based criticism, therefore, cannot be overstated as it forms a strong argument base, close the disconnect between the abstraction of text and actual reality, and importantly gives the reader first-hand knowledge of the prevailing times, conditions, and an understanding of the issue, intention, and message of a literary work. Hence, this study theorizes on the relevance of context and examines it in the creativity of *The Stranger*. It seeks to unveil and establish a co-reference of extraneous and critical internal contextual issues arising from the text that have made the work still relevant today and a continued reference text. It also explores some textual cum creative techniques that inform the context.

Keywords: text, context, contextual criticism, historical circumstances,

Introduction

Context is both internal and external. The former deals with the world created within the text by Camus through the storyline, characters, and setting. This is summed up under textual overview in this article. Though the internal context can be fictional, it does also reflect the external setting. The external context is the real world of reference in which any of its spheres can be put into consideration about the text. On another note, the internal context is said to be the world created and inferred in the text, and the external context is the broad situational context of the non-fictional world from which the author and reader draw (Wales 2014: 86), as it is, inspiration and insight. Further explication of the dual dimensions of context complements what Adrian Beard (2001:146) identified as the author's (external) and text's (internal) contexts. The depth of a text is in the context. The work of Camus is therefore examined through the eye of various levels of contexts. The context examines the background of the author through biographical information. This is the times, life, and experiences of the author and the motivation behind the creation of the text. Although an author might deploy imagination, there is always somehow a connection between an

author's work and life. Imagination and true life experiences are two devices blended in Camus' work.

Contextual criticism digs into the historical and geographical circumstances of the text creation. Writers cannot be isolated from their society. They are often informed by events in the milieu in which they exist. Events before, during, and in the aftermath of the World Wars and prevailing socio-economic and political conditions, for instance, motivate the conception of Camus' work.

Of course, the muse of an author can be triggered by the literary environment. Contextual theory studies the literary environment, popular beliefs, and thoughts that motivate the author. Camus' work sparks the literary currents which are begun by writers, among them Andre Malraux. It is also a rejuvenation of the absurdist literature and movement.

Similarly, contextual criticism does make an inquest into the philosophy and fundamental principles of life. Philosophical context enquires into the unending questions of existence, ethics, and morality in a literary work. There have been various literary movements over time and their accompanying philosophical thoughts. Camus's work is post-war twentieth-century literature, known as modernism, with a prevailing sense of absurdism. The salient issues in Camus's work revolve around the philosophical principles of life, death, time, morality, the nature of God and existence, free will, and the essence of life itself.

A strong base for a contextual critical approach is proved by Ladegaard and Nielson with the averment that context is a series of question(s) "that determines the scope and methodology of literary and cultural research on a given object." The study, therefore deploys the contextual approach to criticism to examine, explain, and describe the contextual issues arising from the text and textual techniques deployed by the writer. This, of course, calls for the qualitative-descriptive method of research.

Trask R. L. (1999: 170) indicates this method of analysis applies to sociolinguistic and conversational analyses. This is whereby language data are described based on the social setting they originate from. *The Stranger* is the primary text in focus, complemented by other secondary texts. References are made and text extracts are derived from the primary text. The text is explained contextually by referencing and 'text extracts' which, according to Halliday & Matthiessen (2014: 22), is an instance of language to making meaning in context. Various contextual and thematic issues as well as creative techniques of the text are therefore exposed to help the reader gain first-hand knowledge and understanding of the text.

Significance of the Study

The study establishes the relevance of context. It shows how the internal and external contexts of the text are co-referential which helps to create a deeper, and better, understanding of the purpose, message, and thematic issues of Camus' *The Stranger*. Since authors are often inspired by real-life cum socio-political events, context becomes imperative for a strong and informed argument of a literary text. This is also often required from students in exams and research writing. The context as well opens up vistas to explore other specific theoretical approaches. The essay, generally, seeks to enhance the understanding of the work through the unveiling and emphasis on its context and thematic issues.

Textual Overview

The Stranger is a very short novel, divided into two parts. In Part One, covering eighteen days, we witness a funeral, a love affair, and a murder. In Part Two, covering about a year, we are presented with a trial that recreates those same eighteen days from various characters' memories and points of view. Part One is full of mostly insignificant days in the life of Meursault, an insignificant man until he commits a murder. Part Two is an attempt, in a courtroom, to judge not only Meursault's

crime but also to judge his life. Camus juxtaposes two worlds: Part One focuses on subjective reality; Part Two, on a more objective, faceted reality.

The Stranger tells the story of Meursault, who lives for the sensual pleasures of the present moment, free of any system of values. Rather than behave by social norms, Meursault tries to live as honestly as he can, doing what he wants to do and befriending those whom he likes. He also refuses to assume feelings that he does not possess. Thus, he does not force himself to cry at his mother's funeral or mourn her death too deeply. A series of events leads to the climactic moment when Meursault haphazardly murders an Arab on the beach; somehow triggered by the atmospheric condition which he could not control. The subsequent trial condemns him not so much for the murder of the Arab but for his lack of commitment to social conventions and sentiments. Free from hope and all restrictions of social conventions, Meursault recognizes himself in a universe without meaning and hope. At the end of the novel, he comes to a full realization and acceptance of his absurd position in the universe and cannot but concludes that he is happy.

Contextual Overview (external context)

In a two-room flat in their poor neighbourhood of Belcourt, Catherine, Camus' mother, works as a Charwoman to feed the family and there is never enough for the family. She displays a piece of the shell that kills her husband and his medals in their sitting room. In *The Stranger*, Camus with the pseudonym of Meursault makes a passing reference to the father as he is told by his mother, who after witnessing a public execution comes back home in nausea and trauma of this event (68). Camus's grandmother is short-tempered and religiously zealous, his uncle sick and his mother economically incapacitated and weary with overwork and often given to long silences amidst this deplorable state. Camus's illness, after he falls with tuberculosis at the tender age of seventeen, engenders the absurd outlook of Camus's life.

Of the literary atmosphere, the leading writers of the 1920s, Proust (1871-1922) and Gide (1869-1951), and a leading magazine, NRF, were concerned with existential matters. Two prominent writers that directly influenced Camus were Andre Malraux and Louis-Ferdinand Celine. Malraux's work *Man's Fate* expounded the view that man is to face his nature of mortality and makes his existence meaningful through political action. While Celine influence on Camus is that both disaccord with the style of the traditional literary discourse of the novel and the opinion that it represents a harmonious universe.

Pessimism was aggravated when Hitler came to power in Germany after Mussolini invaded Abyssinia in 1935. The remilitarization of the Rhineland in 1936 and Franco's rebellion in Spain took place. The attempt of a coup d'etat in France by right-wing extremists led to a riot in February 1934 and this resulted in the unity of the French Left and the victory of the popular front in the election of April 1936. Consequently, the Left encountered many defeats. Camus's disappointment must have been heightened when the popular front prime minister, Leon Blum, lost power in June 1937, and in September 1938, came the Munich Agreement. The preceding year brought the defeat of the Republicans in Spain (Camus's mother's descent). At that time, the war was imminent and seemed inevitable even as Camus fought against it. These events, depression, and the rise of Fascism aroused a cloud of gloom. This climate of unrest and gloom together with events in French-Algeria, were reflected in Camus's early writing.

In French-Algeria were 900,000 Europeans alongside 6 million Arabs at the time when French-Algeria celebrated its centenary of French conquest. With prevailing economic tension, protests arose especially by Arab politicians against the French system of Assimilation and for reform. The Arabs were treated like a conquered population against the policy of assimilating with the French

with all rights and privileges. A nationalistic colonial struggle erupted which was viewed as part of an international struggle of the proletariat. The pied-noir (Half-European and half-African) working class was on one hand in support of the mother country and on the other hand against its policy and plan in Algeria for France's interest appeared to be only in exporting raw materials than in developing industries in Algeria. The pied-noir had to jostle with cheap Arab labour and also suffer from the economic crisis. Meursault in *The Stranger* belongs to this group in French Algeria. Camus under the Pseudonym of Meursault in *The Stranger* is a pied-noir and his writing unveiled the pied-noir culture and disposition, as McCarthy (n.d:10) describes it that through French-Algerian writing and popular culture runs the motif of the pied-noirs, a frontier people. They are pagans as well as unintellectual barbarians; the men are virile and the women sexy; they live through their bodies and are devoted to sport; temperamentally they oscillate between indolence and a frenzied emotion.

Camus left Algeria without a job when the military censorship banned *Alger-Republican*, where he undertook his journalism. He then found a job with *Paris-Soir* to lay out and copy-edit. He finished the manuscript of 'The Stranger' by May of that year. He also worked on the drafts of a play, *Caligula*, and an essay, '[The Myth of Sisyphus](#).' In June, of that year, before the Germans entered Paris, the staff of *Paris-Soir* fled. *Paris-Soir* set up operations in Clermont-Ferrand and Lyon. Camus again lost his job when the staff was reduced. His wish was to return to Algeria. The manuscript of *The Stranger* was revised while Camus was living back in Algeria and then sent an edition to Lyon in April 1941 where Gallimard agreed to publish it. The first edition consisted of 4,400 copies and was very well received in anti-Nazi circles. Sartre's article on the novel launched Camus' career. Thus, Camus as well as Satre actuated preceding writings on the theme of the absurd. According to Howart et al. (1972: 140) "The writings of Samuel Beckett with their bitter sense of the absurdity of existence and a world predicated on death and physical decay, suggest a desperate re-writing of some of Camus's earliest work."

Notably, *The Stranger* is not in the context of the War when it was published in 1942 and read during the gloomy days of the German Occupation. The book sprung from Algerian background and Camus's working class which struck with the themes of the illegitimacy of authority and the importance of concrete individual experience.

Issues in the Novel

These issues arise from the internal context of the novel. Some of these thematic issues include:

Existentialism

Existentialism according to Abrams is a philosophy "centred on 'Dasein,' or "what it is to-be-in-the-world (178)." It emphasizes several points, such as the freedom to choose and the choices an individual makes without the consent of another person or standard. An Existentialist accepts the outcome of his choice and action and is committed to wherever it leads. A recurring existentialist theme is life and death.

The notions of existentialism are embedded in the novel. Meursault freely asserts his person which appears antithetical to social norms. His actions are not much conditioned by himself but by his nature and environment and he accepts full responsibility for the outcome. During the second beach fight when Meursault shoots the Arab, Meursault states that "The scorching blade slashed at my eyelashes and stabbed at my stinging eyes (59)." Meursault shot the Arab because he was uncomfortable and not because he was afraid of the Arab or to defend himself. While he is sent to jail for murder the magistrate wanted to know if he has hired an attorney and he said, "I admitted I hadn't and inquired whether it was really necessary to have one (63)." For he thinks his case is simple, he had murdered a man and he is ready to pay for his action. Meursault assertion of his

existence is bordered by his present mood, activity, need, and desire. Meursault is very much dependent on his present state and instead of looking beyond, he sees Marie as his source of happiness. While in jail, according to him, "I'd have learned to watch for the passing of birds or drifting clouds, as had come to watch for my lawyer's odd neckties, or, in another world, to wait patiently till Sunday for a spell of love-making with Marie (48)."

A striking example of existentialism is presented at the end of the novel when Meursault is sentenced to death; he faces it wholly when the time comes when he says "I felt that I had been happy and that I was happy still (76)." There was no difference between life and death; everything was the same to him. For the first time in the entire novel he realizes what his mother feels before she dies, "So close to death, Maman must have felt free then ready to live it all again (56)." The existentialist belief is that there is no outside force governing our lives. As such, Meursault does not hesitate to draw the inevitable conclusion of life.

Meursault's freedom of how he lives and feels towards life is manifest in the lack of grief at his mother's death, little joy at Marie's love, little pleasure at the boss's offer of a promotion, and little, if any, remorse for his crime. He expresses no anger and hardly any regret even at the loss of his freedom. He seemingly feels no resentment toward Raymond, who draws him into the quarrel with the Arabs, nor towards his lawyer, who handles his case poorly, and the outcome of the court's judgment which condemns him to death. To him, these are mere basics of existence and do not change anything about life and inevitable death. His continued indifference to the world ultimately leads to his death. In the end, Camus demonstrates that from his perspective, the human condition has no greater meaning than the facts of existence: we live, we die.

Morality, Amorality, and Immorality

Morality entails conforming to the standard and principles of right behaviour socially and religiously. Being immoral suggests not adhering to ethical or moral principles and in-between morality and immorality is the psychological state of being amoral, that is lacking a sense of morality or immorality. Camus's absurdist philosophy implies that moral orders have no rational or natural basis. Yet Camus did not approach the world with moral indifference, and he believes that life's lack of a "higher" meaning which morality can only attain should not necessarily lead one to despair.

The character of Meursault in *The Stranger* could be ascribed to being amoral. He is one without qualms and with a simple conscience as in living in a society without adhering to or being guided by its social and religious values and ethics. A prominent feature of Meursault's amorality is his lack of scruples in helping Raymond. He never considers the moral or immoral implications. When Raymond requires Meursault to contrive a letter for him to punish his suspiciously unfaithful girlfriend, Meursault states "I wrote the letter. I didn't take much trouble over it, but I wanted to satisfy Raymond, as I'd no reason not to satisfy him (22)." Meursault has no qualms about helping Raymond as long as he can help. To Meursault, nothing means anything, and anything could be done as long as one's nature is inclined to it. However, this does not obliterate Camus as a persistent humanist. He is noted for his faith in man's dignity in the face of what he saw as a cold, indifferent universe.

Absurdism

There has been the traditional belief and culture that humans are fairly rational creatures living in a fairly intelligible universe. However, this belief was no longer so after the 1940s, especially in the existential philosophy of Jean-Paul Satre and Albert Camus, who see humans as isolated

existent on a fruitless search in an alien meaningless universe (Abrams 2012: 1). Similarly, in Garnet Rees' own words (1979: 79), "the experience of Absurdity born of man's existence in the world has many constituent elements. There is the brevity of man's life and the swift passing of time. Meursault faces trial and a death sentence in his 30s. He states thus if one does not die now, one will surely die later." And so during his imprisonment, Meursault attempts a suitable means of passing his time without feeling bored or apprehensive of his fate. Rees queries the fact that for the Christian, there can be the saving grace of God but what happens to man when God is dead, for there is then no absolute authority for the traditional distinction between good and evil, right and wrong? And he concludes, thus, Life has not an established meaning but is chaos on which each man must seek to establish his order (55). The opening sentences of the novel embody Meursault's absurdist outlook on life, his emotional indifference and detachment from people, and his passive but quiet alienation from the rest of society. He doesn't even know which day his mother died, and to him, it "doesn't mean anything" anyway; "Maman died today. Or yesterday maybe, I don't know. I got a telegram from the home: 'Mother deceased. Funeral tomorrow. Faithfully yours.' That doesn't mean anything. Maybe it was yesterday (4)." The Nurse also at the Home says, "If you go slowly, you risk getting sunstroke. But if you go too fast, you work up a sweat and then catch a chill inside the church." She was right. There was no way out (12)." The nurse speaks of both the weather and the human condition. The sun's heat is inescapable, just as death is inescapable. There was no way out except through acceptance. The mechanical nature of man's work imposed on him by an industrial society constitutes the absurd and this can be deduced from Meursault's speech, "It occurred to me that anyway one more Sunday was over that Maman was buried now, that I was going back to work, and that, really, nothing had changed (11)."

Meursault's worldview manifests in his encounter with the chaplain, he demonstrates that nothing really matters, since we all live and we all die, and what we do in between these two basic facts is inessential. Meursault's knowledge of life is revealed as he says,

"And I felt ready to live it all again too. As if that blind rage had washed me clean, rid me of hope; for the first time, in that night alive with signs and stars, I opened myself to the gentle indifference of the world. Finding it so much like myself—so like a brother, really—I felt that I had been happy and that I was happy again (76)."

Meursault realizes the absurdity of his existence in the universe and accepts his fate. David Galens (2002: 60) opines that in absurdist philosophy while "morality, religion, science, and philosophy purport to discover unchanging universal principles and values,...death chance and the impenetrability of human motives render life essentially incomprehensible and controvert claims for transcendent meaning" While in prison, awaiting his execution, Meursault comes to realize that just as he had lived his life one way, he could just as well have lived it another...and nothing would matter (74)." For him, according to Michelman (2008: 266), "life is absurd."

Nihilism

When *The Stranger* was first published in 1942, in the context of the prevailing war and Occupation, the book was celebrated for its focus on the illegitimacy of authority, a world without values, and the primacy of the individual. It soon became a classic of French literature in many circles and Camus was quickly recognized as a great French/European writer of the 1940s. Nihilism is a revolutionary doctrine that recommends the destruction of the social system for its own sake. The French-Algerian struggle against French supremacy that subjects the Arabs as conquered of a conqueror as with all social systems of authority is a prevailing theme underlying the background of *The Stranger*. The idea of nihilism can be deduced in respect of Meursault's encounter with the Home and the law court as government institutions and as well the judge that

is set up to subjugate the individual's natural disposition as it serves as hypocrisy to the outcome of life and death.

Atheism

Is Meursault an Atheist? No. Meursault's rejection of the belief in God is meant to state that to live life to the fullest is essential and not because there is God or that we hope to live with Him. The simple message of Camus's atheism is that if there is another life to live, it is inconsequential to this present life that we ought to live. Meursault's honesty is perhaps his only meritorious quality. Meursault is an anti-hero who does not believe in God but cannot lie. He refuses to join the hypocritical band of those who profess their faith in God and deny that the world is not for them to live in. He does believe in going to the movies, swimming, and making love. He is finally beheaded because he murdered an Arab. Bower (1971: 50) has helped to buttress this fact as he explains that "Far from making a plea for evil, his first impulse, at least, is to plead for justice which he ranks above divinity. He does not deny the existence of God. He refutes Him in the name of a moral value."

The Impassivity of Nature

Nature plays a prominent role in *The Stranger* and serves as the onus of all activities and actions. Camus is brought up in Algeria, a country that is exposed to sunlight and the plain by the Mediterranean Sea. The sun and the sea have been recurring motifs in Camus's writings including *The Stranger*. Meursault describes vividly the atmosphere and what it is capable of engendering, thus:

"Wherever I looked I saw the same sun-drenched countryside, and the sky was so dazzling that I dared not raise my eyes. Presently we struck a patch of freshly tarred road. A shimmer of heat played over it and one's feet squelched at each step, leaving bright black gashes. In front, the coachman's glossy black hat looked like a lump of the same sticky substance, poised above the hearse. It gave one a queer, dreamlike impression, that blue-white glare overhead and all this blackness round one: the sleek black of the hearse, the dull black of the men's clothes, and the silvery-black gashes in the road. And then there were the smells, smells of hot leather and horse dung from the hearse, veined with whiffs of incense smoke. What with these and the hangover from a poor night's sleep, I found my eyes and thoughts growing blurred (12)."

It is that nature has a powerful effect on man which may engender images and feelings and cause him to act irrationally or out of impulse as Meursault tells the judges honestly "It is because of the sun (55)," in their query of him shooting the Arab and again he asserts that his physical condition at any moment often influenced his feelings (41). But then Nature cannot be held to ransom which makes the world even more irrational. Nature, therefore is impassive to the plight of man. Rather to put our hope in an afterlife that often is a temporal consolation; we must accept it so and live it. Brian Masters (1979: 18) referencing Robert Champigny rightly puts it that "Meursault is an epicurean hero of pagan stock, a man who seeks harmony with the natural world in opposition to the Christian, who withdraws from the world. The pagan enjoys physical contact with the world, avoids abstractions which cannot bring happiness, adopts to what he has and makes the most of it."

Chance/Fate

Chance plays an integral role in the life of man and this is often engendered by an impassive world. During his trial, Meursault explains thus,

"The Prosecutor, who had his back half turned to me, said, without

looking in my direction, that, subject to His Honor's approval, he would like to know if I'd gone back to the stream with the intention of killing the Arab. I said, "No." In that case, why had I taken a revolver with me, and why go back precisely to that spot? I said it was a matter of pure chance (55)."

Fate as well plays a prominent role in man's life as chance. Meursault in his rumination of mind observes, "This was the same hour, but with a difference; I was returning to a cell, and what awaited me was a night haunted by forebodings of the coming day. And so I learned that familiar paths traced in the dusk of summer evenings may lead as well to prisons as to innocent, untroubled sleep (61)." Therefore, Chance, fate, or destiny are forces that one cannot control or escape from but have made the world absurd to man.

Fact against Sentiment

One thing people have often shielded away from is fact and refusing to face the fact takes recourse to sentiment. The novel upheld the ideal of fact as against the exudation of sentiment. Meursault's disclosure of facts makes him a non-conformist to the general sentimentality of the people. The people in the court loathed Meursault because he is very blatant with the truth of fact, that he killed an Arab is a matter of fact without sensation. The turnout of his crime in which he was condemned is because he did not express any form of social sentiments for the dead as is expected. It is a matter of fact when his boss tells him if a change of life wouldn't appeal to him and Meursault's reply is, "...one never changed his way of life; one life was as good as another, and my present one suited me quite well (28)."

It is a matter of sentiment when Salamano becomes too attached to his dog and wants the poor creature to reciprocate the love he desires. Meursault's condemnation is based on the general social sentiments he had refused to express. Meursault is apathetic and does not, by the hypocrisy of sentiments, betray the facts of life. The novel mocks all sentimental expressions toward the inevitable and evitable occurrences of life, such as death, marriage, and promotion. Whatever that be in life is a fact that we must accept without the hypocrisy of sentiments.

Reality and Idea

Love, ambition, justice, Marriage, and other social conventions are merely ideas and are less meaningful. The more meaningful thing is the reality of our life, as it is. Meursault's reply to his boss about his ambition of having a change of life is that one never changed his way of life and that one's life was as good as another, and his present one suited him quite well (28). When Marie asked Meursault if he loves her, Meursault replies that her question meant nothing or next to nothing (29). Also when the lawyer inquired if Meursault has chosen a lawyer to defend himself, he answered, "No," he hadn't thought about it, and asked him if he needed to have one (40). For he said he regarded his case as very simple (40). It is that people often live in disguise of their true nature but subject themselves to social conventions. People are not being realistic but live in the pretense of ideologies and thus man is not in accord with his natural disposition. Masters asserts, "We do not have to live with idea (18)."

Good, Evil, and the Conscience of Man

All the other characters are like every other person except Meursault. Mariane says she likes him because he is queer. Because Meursault has no qualms, he acts and speaks innocently out of the purity of his conscience. He does not know good or evil. His is a conscience that transcends the wage of sin. A Christian tenet teaches that the wage of sin is death. Meursault does not feel he owes the debt of sin neither does he feel the redemption of righteousness. And so he rejects both God and Satan but asserts his person as the ultimate of life. Therefore, if there is a God and God

is to judge Meursault, God cannot hold him responsible for what he does not know. Meursault exudes a childish innocence which exonerates him from all blame. According to Masters, Camus said if he were to write a book on Ethics, there would be 100 pages out of which 99 would be blank. On the last page, would be 'I know of only one duty and that is to love (9).'

Point of View

Camus uses the first-person narrative point of view as an individual narrating his personal experience and relating to us his thoughts, speeches, and actions. He also uses the third person limited narrative point of view as a firsthand witness and participant of other characters' experiences. He is only limited to what other characters say or do without prying into their inner minds. By this, Camus only makes conjectures of what he thinks and leaves them for the readers to judge. This style of point of view has made the novel very objective to suggest contextually the forthrightness of the nom de plume narrator, Meursault.

Language

Camus's language is simple and objective and while using the first-person narrative point of view and the third-person limited narrative point of view, he does not achieve any personal preferences which make the general language of the novel impersonal. There are perhaps two aspects of language in the novel. First is the formal and authoritative language of the 'Home' where Meursault's mother died and the court of law; both of which are government and public institutions in which the general sentiments of the people could be said to be lodged. Second is the less formal and neutral or indifferent language of Meursault. For example, the telegram sent by the home reads "Your mother passed away. Funeral tomorrow. Deep sympathy. Sincerely Yours (4)." And Meursault states that doesn't mean anything (4), in response to the sentiment of death and the implied command of being at the funeral; and uses the phrases 'perhaps' and 'I don't know.' The incongruity of both languages differentiates Meursault, making him a stranger to these public institutions. The language used by Camus allows the reader to make a judgment rather than imposing it.

Narrative Style

Camus's artistic expression very much blends with his intended perspective of the novel. That is, the impersonal style adopted can achieve a vivid exposition of the subject matter. Through a factual and impartial account, the novel imposes no ideology but leaves the bulk of inferences to the reader. With less use of adjectives, there are fewer tendencies for fantasizing which makes the novel credible. The first part of the novel presents the narrator as being a passive participant in life who only tells us what he sees or hears or does. The accumulation of his experiences makes up the second part of the novel and thus, makes him an active participant. In this second phase of life, the author uses the stream-of-consciousness technique to reveal to us the mind of the narrator. Ironically, in the first part of the novel we may have thought the narrator, Meursault despises life by being apathetic, but in the second part through the stream of consciousness, we find he values life. It is his accusers (escapists) who devalue life.

Motifs

Motifs are unifying ideas in literary works. They are recurring structures or devices that can help to develop and inform the text's major themes.

Decay and death

Death and decay, a recurring idea, pervades the novel. The work is informed in the context of a natural death, the accidental death of a murder committed, a death sentence, and a social system that is unwilling to admit and accept the inevitable decay of all existing. Salamano loves his decaying scab-covered dog and he values its companionship and never wants to let go although

the poor creature cannot bring itself to adapt. Meursault does not show much emotion in response to his mother's death, but the society in which he lives expected him to grieve. However, Meursault accords to death's inevitability which to him is the complete and final end of life.

Watching and observing

The novel is fraught with instances of other characters watching Meursault, or of Meursault watching them which connotes humanity's endless search for purpose or meaning in life. The old inmates at the Home watch Meursault as if to implicate him with their being lodged awaiting death. The people in the courtroom watch Meursault as part of the judgment and in a bid to find an essence against the background of the set social norms they conform with. Meursault also from his balcony watches people but passively. The Arabs watch Raymond and his friends with implicit antagonism as they walk to the bus. The neighbours watch as witnesses to the flouting of social decorum when Raymond fights with his mistress. Meursault watches the woman at Celeste's, and afterward, she watches him in court. The activity of watching and observing is geared towards the question of life, "Why?"

Eating, working, and swimming

These activities and even more, sex, run through the novel. What these suggest is the importance of the physical human world; the need to live in full the present life rather than to deny oneself these necessities in the hope of another life. Meursault is fond of always voicing his need for food and dining in the company of others. His routines also consist of working and going out to swim or feeling to have sexual intercourse with Marie. What it entails to live life is all-inclusive of these, and even more important than spiritual, emotional, and social subjectivity.

Symbols

Symbols are objects, characters, figures, or colours used to represent abstract ideas or concepts.

The courtroom

The courtroom in *The Stranger* symbolizes society as a whole and as an institution that conserves social norms. The law functions as the will of the people in which their sentiments are lodged, and the jury sits in judgment on behalf of the entire people. In *The Stranger*, virtually all the characters were present in Court as witnesses. The court attempts to construct a logical explanation for the irrational events of the universe as Meursault often explains his actions based on the events of chance, fate, or natural phenomena. The attempt to construct a logical explanation for unexplainable circumstances is seen as futile.

The crucifix

The crucifix that the examining magistrate waves at Meursault symbolizes Christianity. Christianity conceives of a rational order for the universe based on God's creation and direction of the world which endues human life with higher metaphysical meaning. The chaplain's insistence that Meursault turns to God does not directly represent a desire that Meursault embraces the Christian religion but that he embraces the principle of a meaningful universe. When Meursault defies the magistrate by rejecting Christianity, he implicitly rejects all systems that seek to define a rational order within human existence. Therefore Meursault becomes, to the social order of which the people commit their essence, a threat.

Conclusion

The Stranger is a chef-d'oeuvre viewed from its context and thematic issues. However, John Ellis (1997: 35) has argued a literary text should not be taken as part of its context of origin. In the advent and thoughts of various schools of criticism about the (literary) text and context, the context remains paramount to understanding the text (Gaganpreet Walia 2014: 322) as has been demonstrated. Kovala quoting Lawrence Grossberg pointed out that context is both the starting

point and end of analysis at the same time... and also often invisible in a text which must be made visible by a theoretical contextualist framework (159). And as observed by V. G. Kalashnikov (2016: 155), "diverse environments of the existence of the personality and works of the artist as the unified system of contexts psychological in essence have not been considered yet." Much, therefore, still needs to be done and explored on the contextual approach.

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